

Biomethanation of pretreated vegetables wastes

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Manuscript received 13 March 2000, revised 22 August 2000, accepted 12 November 2001

The results suggest that methane production is almost negligible with fresh vegetables (brinjal and cucumber) alone suggesting that they lack proper inocula for biomethanation. However, pretreated vegetables when used with dung samples produce appreciable methane though the dung samples are not equally effective for biomethanation. Rotten cucumbers appear to be better substrates.

Large reserve of renewable plant and animal biomass resources (i.e. non-conventional energy sources) can be profitably utilized for generating clean fuel and it appears to be most desirable energy option¹ for a country like India. Among the large variety of available biomass², market wastes containing enormous amounts of vegetables can be regarded as the potential source of carbon for biomethanation by anaerobic digestion. However, development of the digestion process requires considerable investment. Naturally, assessment of economics of producing methane, i.e. overall cost benefit analysis must be made prior to utilizing the market wastes for commercial production of biogas as the biomethanation of market wastes are likely to be non-reliable in character due to variable availability of C-content and impurities as in case of domestic refuse³. Moreover, pretreatment of biomass like acid hydrolysis⁴ or other treatments⁵, pulverization etc. should be carried out prior to anaerobic digestion to increase the yield of methane. Extensive studies on the different aspects of biomethanation had been carried out in our laboratory^{6,7}.

It has been considered desirable to undertake laboratory experiments for quantitative estimation of methane produced when common vegetables (market wastes or domestic refuse) like brinjal and cucumber (either alone or in mixed form) are subjected to anaerobic digestion without addition of inoculum or with addition of different dung samples (cow, goat, buffalo, pig etc.) as source of wild population of microbes⁶. The results are described in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) indicated that CH₄ production was always higher in anoxic condition than that in the atmospheric conditions. But the results definitely suggested that methane production was possible even in atmospheric conditions. The methane production was very negligible with

fresh cucumber and brinjal. Appreciable methane production was observed with rotten vegetables with dung or sewage samples as inocula.

Methane production was found to be low when poultry waste was used as inoculum. The low production of methane with sewage sample must be due to low carbon content in the inoculum. Rotten brinjal did not produce much methane with cow and buffalo dung as inocula but appreciable methane production was observed with rotten cucumber.

It is not difficult to ascribe the reasons for very small methane production with rotten vegetables without dung samples as inocula even in anoxic conditions. They definitely lack the consortium of bacteria needed for biomethanation. Rather, they possess microbes which inhibit anaerobic digestions. In fact, different microbes were isolated from these rotten vegetables aerobically by petridish plating technique using different fungal and algal media. Colony of different microbes like pseudomonas, fungi etc. were grown. They were isolated and maintained in sterile slant tubes containing the respective nutrient media. However, we were unable to carryout further testing with these isolates.

Experimental

The vegetables (brinjal and cucumber) were collected from the local market. Pretreatment of the fresh vegetables was done with their rotten counterpart. Fresh samples were crushed and kept as such under aerobic conditions in glass containers. They were then inoculated with their own crushed rotten sources for pretreatment.

A definite amount (0.1 g or 0.5 g + 0.5 g) or the pretreated substrates (brinjal and cucumber) was dispensed in each of the 15 ml vials and was diluted (1 : 2, w/v) to make slurry. In other sets, substrates were mixed with dung

Table 1. Biomethanation of various pretreated vegetable wastes

	% Methane produced at different days interval (× 24 h)				
	7	15	19	23	27
(a) Control sets :					
Dung (1×10^{-3} kg) :					
Cow	39.5	47.2	50.8	35.9	23.1
Buffalo	38.1	48.1	31.8	22.0	16.8
Poultry	36.3	41.3	34.0	27.7	14.5
Pig	23.6	43.6	34.5	22.7	16.3
Goat	34.5	45.9	41.8	32.0	28.6
Sewage (Jagaddal, 1×10^{-3} dm ³)	22.2	43.1	40.4	28.1	10.4
(b) Pretreated sets :					
Rotten brinjal (1×10^{-3} kg) without Ar	–	3.1	4.5	5.4	10.9
Rot. brin. (1×10^{-3} kg) with Ar	–	6.3	8.1	9.0	19.3
Rot. brin. + fresh brin. $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg without Ar	–	–	6.8	10.9	10.0
Rot. brin. + fresh brin. $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	–	0.9	8.6	15.9	21.8
Rot. brin. + cow dung $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	6.3	7.7	9.4	17.2	20.0
Rot. brin. + buff. dung $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	5.2	8.6	15.9	21.8	25.0
Rot. brin. + poul. waste $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	3.6	5.4	7.7	13.6	19.5
Rot. brin. + pig. waste $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	22.7	63.6	62.7	61.3	60.9
Rot. brin. + goat dung $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	55.4	67.2	71.3	70.5	70.1
Rot. brin. + sewage $(0.5 \times 10^{-3}$ kg + 0.5×10^{-3} dm ³) with Ar	10.1	20.4	27.7	32.7	39.0
Rotten cucumber (1×10^{-3} kg) without Ar	–	3.1	6.3	8.6	13.1
Rot. cuc. (1×10^{-3} kg) with Ar	9.2	9.5	10.0	11.3	16.3
Rot. cuc. + fresh cuc. $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg without Ar	–	–	–	–	–
Rot. cuc. + fresh cuc. $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	2.7	3.6	0.9	–	–
Rot. cuc. + cow dung $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	37.7	48.0	63.1	50.4	37.7
Rot. cuc. + buff. dung $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	15.4	62.0	68.1	70.1	59.8
Rot. cuc. + poul. waste $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	0.9	5.4	7.7	10.9	21.3
Rot. cuc. + pig. waste $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	25.4	56.8	63.0	64.5	65.9
Rot. cuc. + goat dung $(0.5 + 0.5) \times 10^{-3}$ kg with Ar	61.3	66.8	70.0	71.0	71.0
Rot. cuc. + sewage $(0.5 \times 10^{-3}$ kg + 0.5×10^{-3} dm ³) with Ar	13.6	22.0	35.9	40.0	47.2

samples or sewage as source of wild population of microbes (Table 1). The vials were fitted with latex corks, crimped with aluminium foils and subjected to digestion under anoxic conditions by passing Iolar II argon gas for several minutes. Similar experiments were made under atmospheric conditions. Suitable control experiments were also carried out. pH of the samples was adjusted to 7–8. The inoculation and filling of the vials were done under aseptic condition using a Klenzaid laminar flow apparatus.

The digestion was carried out at 37°. The methane production was followed by withdrawing 2 ml of biogas produced from the headspace at different time intervals and the methane produced was estimated quantitatively by gas chromatography (Netal Omega QC) using a silica gel column and hydrogen flame ionization detector using N₂ as the carrier gas. The instrument was previously calibrated with standard and pure methane gas (E.D.T. Research, London; 5.21% methane in nitrogen gas \equiv 100% CH₄).

Nitrogen, hydrogen and air (Iolar grade II) were obtained from the Indian Oxygen Company. The contents of the vials were rejected after each measurement. The methane content represents the commulative value of methane in the headspace.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank MNES, Government of India, for financial support. The authors also thank Dr. S. Dutta, formerly a Research Associate, for help.

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